

Performance Tasks-Enriched Material in Cookery 9 for Enhancing the Practical Skills of Students

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ABSTRACT: The purpose of this study is to improve the practical skills of students in Cookery 9- Prepare Sandwiches by evaluating the effectiveness of a researcher-created learning material that will assist in addressing a low level of performance skills in Cookery 9. The Pearson-Product Moment Correlation was used whether there is a significant relationship between the Performance Tasks-Enriched Materials and the level of proficiency in Practical Skills of the student-respondents in Cookery 9. Further, descriptive-developmental research was used in this study for the acceptance level of the designed performance tasks-enrich intervention materials using the perception of the respondents and the student's proficiency after using the performance tasks-enriched materials. Data were collected from 35 Grade 9 - Cattleya students enrolled in Callejon National High School from 2022-2023 using a pretest and posttest, performance task-enriched material, and a survey questionnaire. According to the findings, the students were generally proficient in their practical skills in Cookery 9. They perceived the performance task-enriched material to be effective in terms of perform mise'en place, prepare variety of sandwiches, present variety of sandwiches and store sandwiches. Their level of mastery, as well as their perception of effectiveness, are significantly related to their pre- and post-test scores. After using the developed material, the learners progressed from the beginning and developing level of performance to approaching proficiency and proficient levels. These findings imply that performance task-enriched material in students' performance tasks improved their practical skills..

KEYWORDS: Cookery 9, Performance Task-Enriched Material, Practical Skills, Prepare Sandwiches.

INTRODUCTION

21st century education focuses on providing students with the skills they need to thrive in this new world and helping them develop the confidence to put those skills into practice[1]. A school is a vital institution that can provide students with great opportunities. Adhering to the curriculum, as mandated by the Department of Education, Technology and Livelihood Education is a subject matter that the community needs, particularly in providing practical knowledge and skills of vocational and technological efficiency, as well as solving realistic problems. [2] Teaching practical skills is not the same as teaching knowledge or theory, and it necessitates some special considerations. [3] A performance task is any learning or assessment activity that involves students showing their knowledge, understanding, and competence. [4]

The study was anchored on constructivist learning, a learning theory that describes how people learn. According to Seel, learning occurs when students construct meaning by interpreting information in the context of their own experiences. Individual, social, cognitive, and postmodern constructivist learning theories all emphasize that learners construct knowledge through their activities and interpret concepts and principles in terms of the schemata that they have already developed.[5]

The study adopted an instructional design to guide the research procedure. Instructional Design (also known as Instructional System Design (ISD)) is the practice of creating instructional experiences that make knowledge and skill acquisition more efficient, effective, and appealing. The various phases of the ADDIE Model have been discussed on the Cullata website [6]

Since the Performance Task-Enriched Material was used as an indicator to determine how to improve the student's practical cooking skills, it is vital to understand which skills should be covered under the practical to maximize the potential for describing the competency. For a variety of reasons, practical skills can be difficult for students to master. No matter what the cause, understanding the skills engaged and which ones your learner struggles with can help you get the right help. The five key elements of ICARE's learning experience for children and adults are an introduction, connection, application, reflection, and extension according to Hidayat. The use of the ICARE system ensures that participants can put what they have learned into practice.[7]

Hampton in his study, teaching practical skills requires using very precise instructions to enable the learner to follow the process and repeat the skill. It certainly requires special skills in an instructor if there are no visuals. For open and distance learners, the

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most frequently used method for teaching practical skills is using print-based illustrations of step-by-step procedures. This method still has its shortcomings, of course, and substitutes are required.[8]

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The researcher found a low level of performance skills in Grade 9 learners in Cookery. Thus, the researcher recognizes that she was interested in designing learning material in Cookery 9 so that the learners have adequate material to be used to improve their practical skills despite the changes of today. The Study will aim to enhance the practical skills of students in Cookery 9 with performance tasks-enriched material to enhance their skill in the area. The content of the performance task-enriched material covers the different aspects of practical skills in Cookery such as clean, sanitize, and store kitchen tools and equipment, clean and sanitize kitchen premises, perform mise' en place, prepare sandwiches, present sandwiches, store sandwiches and lastly package food items. Therefore, the researcher conceptualized the study.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

Descriptive-developmental research was used in this study because it aimed at the acceptance level of the designed performance tasks-enriched materials using the perception of the respondents and the student's proficiency after using the performance tasks-enriched materials.[9]

Specifically, this research utilized a correlational research design. A correlational research design investigates relationships between variables without the researcher controlling or manipulating any of them. [10]

Research Procedure

The research procedure adopted the ADDIE Model.

Phase I. Analysis Phase

In this phase, the researcher analysed the least learned competencies of the learners using the pre-test in the third quarter. Then, the researcher determined the topics and competencies which are included in the performance task-enriched material.

Phase II. Design Phase

After determining the topics to be included the researcher designed performance task-enriched material. Each learning competency consists of five parts. First is the Introduction, this part contains the objectives to be focused on what the learners are expected to learn and the topics to be discussed. Second is the Connect, this part of the performance task-enriched material shows the discussions, detail of practical skills, and examples and is connected to their prior knowledge. The third is the application, this part helps the learners to discover and develop their skills and contains performance tasks. Fourth is Reflection, in this part of the material, the learner takes some time to reflect on what they've learned as they've moved from connecting and applying. Lastly is Extension, this part offers the learners opportunities to individualize learning experiences. The researcher also included rubrics for the practical skills of the learners.

Phase III. Development Phase

The researcher prepared the performance tasks-enriched material to validate and evaluate the module.

Phase IV. Implement Phase

After the research instrument was validated and revised. The researcher utilized the performance tasks-enriched materials. The learners have their materials during the implementation of the study.

Phase V. Evaluation Phase

After the implementation period, the respondents evaluated the content of the intervention materials and their acceptability using the given questionnaires.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows the summary of the student's perceptions of the adaptability, appropriateness, consistency, usability, and aesthetic value of the performance tasks-enriched material. It shows that respondents thought the material was highly acceptable, with a rating of 3.71 and a standard deviation of 0.29. It means that the material establishes an appropriate performance task for the learner that is aligned with the objective and meets their needs. As a result, students have more chances to improve their skills by responding to and performing performance task-enrichment material.

The Performance Tasks-Enriched Material captures the learners' attention and interest, allowing them to enjoy answering and performing the performance task, is usable for learners and teachers, and adapts to the learner's needs in order to help them learn and improve their practical skills, indicating that the learning material is highly acceptable in the respondents.

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Table 1. Summary Table for Respondent's Perceived Acceptance Level of the Performance Tasks-Enriched Material.

Level of Acceptability	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
Adaptability	3.63	0.28	Highly Acceptable
Appropriateness	3.69	0.29	Highly Acceptable
Consistency	3.77	0.29	Highly Acceptable
Usability	3.69	0.32	Highly Acceptable
Aesthetic Value	3.79	0.25	Highly Acceptable
Total	3.71	0.29	Highly Acceptable

Legend: 3.26-4.00 - Very Much Satisfied/Highly Acceptable, 2.51-3.25- Satisfied/Acceptable, 1.76-2.50 Moderately Satisfied/Slightly Acceptable, 1.00-1.75 Not Satisfied/Not Acceptable

Table 2. Summary Table for Perception of the Respondents in the Performance Tasks-Enriched Material

Material Content	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
Introduction	3.67	0.34	Strongly Agree
Connect	3.74	0.29	Strongly Agree
Application	3.67	0.29	Strongly Agree
Reflection	3.74	0.28	Strongly Agree
Extension	3.73	0.27	Strongly Agree
Total	3.71	0.29	Strongly Agree

Legend: 3.26-4.00 - Strongly Agree/Highly Appropriate, 2.51-3.25- Agree/Appropriate, 1.76-2.50 – Disagree/Slightly Appropriate, 1.00-1.75 Strongly Disagree/Not Appropriate

Table 2 shows on the next page summarize students' perceptions of the respondents in the performance tasks-Enriched Material. It demonstrates that respondents strongly agreed with the material, with a rating of 3.71 and a standard deviation of 0.29.

It means that the learning content of the performance tasks-enriched material gives clarification for the student, allowing them to better understand their lesson; it also assists students in connecting new knowledge learned in the lesson with something previously learned or experienced in daily life, assisting them in applying what they learned from the lesson and making more sense when applied to real-life situations; and students have the opportunity to share what they learned from the lesson

The table 3 depicts the distribution of students' Pre-Test Scores in Practical Skills. As shown, ratings of 3-4 or developing level of performance in Store Sandwiches in the pretest yielded the highest frequency count of 27, while ratings of 7-8 yielded the lowest frequency count of one. The student, as well as the others, did not comprehend the practical skills in store sandwiches. This suggests that the majority of students are still working on improving their skills in perform mis en place, prepare a variety of sandwiches, present a variety of sandwiches, and store sandwiches. In some categories, only a small number of students performed proficient or advanced, highlighting areas of strength within the group. Overall, there is room for improvement, and additional instruction is required to achieve higher levels of proficiency in preparing sandwiches. This implies that students have limited knowledge and skill in perform mise'en place, prepare a variety of sandwiches, present a variety of sandwiches, and store sandwiches.

Table 3. Distribution of Pre test Scores of the Students in Practical Skills

Scores	Perform Mis En Place		Prepare a Variety of Sandwiches		Present a Variety of Sandwiches		Store Sandwiches		Verbal Interpretation
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	
9-10	0	0.00	2	5.71	0	0.00	0	0.00	Advanced
7-8	12	34.29	9	25.71	0	0.00	1	2.86	Proficient
5-6	16	45.71	13	37.14	10	28.57	4	11.43	Approaching Proficiency
3-4	5	14.29	9	25.71	22	62.86	27	77.14	Developing
0-2	2	5.71	2	5.71	3	8.57	3	8.57	Beginning
Total	35	100	35	100	35	100	35	100	

Legend: 9-10- Advanced, 7-8 – Proficient, 5–6 Approaching Proficiency, 3 – 4 Developing, 0-2 - Beginning

The table 4 illustrates the distribution of post-test scores in practical skills among students. The proficient level in perform mise' en place in practical skills with scores of 7-8 had the highest frequency count of 24 or 68.57% during the posttest. In-store sandwiches with a developing level of 3-4 had the lowest frequency count of 1 or 2.86%.

In general, the majority of students performed proficient level in the criteria of preparing a variety of sandwiches, while fewer students advanced or approached proficiency in the criteria of performing mis en place and presenting a variety of sandwiches. Furthermore, a small number of students met the developing level in the criteria of preparing a variety of sandwiches and storing sandwiches.

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Table 4. Distribution of Post test Scores of the Students in Practical Skills

Scores	Perform Mis En Place		Prepare a Variety of Sandwiches		Present a Variety of Sandwiches		Store Sandwiches		Verbal Interpretation
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	
9-10	6	17.14	6	17.14	0	0.00	9	25.71	Advanced Proficient Approaching Proficiency Developing Beginning
7-8	24	68.57	16	45.71	13	37.14	17	48.57	
5-6	3	8.57	9	25.71	17	48.57	8	22.86	
3-4	2	5.71	4	11.43	5	14.29	1	2.86	
0-2	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	
Total	35	100	35	100	35	100	35	100	

Legend: 9-10- Advanced, 7-8 – Proficient, 5–6 Approaching Proficiency, 3 – 4 Developing, 0-2 - Beginning

Subsequently, the learner applied the performance task-enriched material. The post-test results of the learners differ from the pre-test results. The learner provides a correct answer to the question. Through performance tasks provided in the learning material, the materials help the learner in understanding and practice practical skills. The performance task helps the student in perform mise'en place, prepare a variety of sandwiches, present variety of sandwiches and store sandwiches. The learner gained skill as a result of the performance task in the learning material.

This result find support from the study by Villonez [11],” revealed that the experimental group's performance was greatly improved by the use of strategic intervention material (SIM). It is possible to conclude that the performance of students in the experimental group improved significantly when SIM was used to teach the lesson. As a result, the use of SIM was more successful and efficient than the use of traditional methods in teaching various scientific topics. Furthermore, it was suggested that SIM be used as an instructional resource or approach in the teaching of science lessons, as well as other topics.

Table 5 reveals the test difference between the pretest and posttest scores of the learners in terms of practical skills.

Table 5. Level of Proficiency in Practical Skills

Practical Skills	Pretest		Interpretation	Post Test		Interpretation
	Mean	Std. Deviation		Mean	Std. Deviation	
Perform Mise' en Place	5.77	1.88	Approaching Proficiency	7.49	1.22	Proficient
Prepare a Variety of Sandwiches	5.57	2.03	Approaching Proficiency	6.83	1.76	Proficient
Present a Variety of Sandwiches	3.83	1.07	Developing	5.94	1.35	Approaching Proficiency
Store Sandwiches	3.63	1.06	Developing	7.46	1.44	Proficient

Legend: 8.01 and 10.00- Advanced, 6.01-8.00 – Proficient, 4.01 – 6.00 Approaching Proficiency, 2.01 – 4.00 Developing, 0.00 and 2.00 – Beginning

The data showed that after the use of the designed performance tasks-enriched material there is an increase in the level of proficiency. The mean of the Perform Mise' en Place pretest is 5.77, increasing to 7.49. In Prepare a Variety of Sandwiches from 5.57 in pretest became to 6.83 in posttest. In Present a Variety of Sandwiches begins at 3.83 and turn to 5.94. In Store Sandwiches starts from 3.63, it lasts to 7.46. It can be perceived the learners perform better using the designed performance tasks-enriched material and that from the developing level they were able to reach a proficient level.

As the results show, no one performed well on the pretest in terms of practical skills. The pre-test questions required students to perform mise'en place, prepare a variety of sandwiches, present a variety of sandwiches, and store sandwiches. The majority of students struggled and failed the Store Sandwiches practical skills. The pre-test results revealed that the students' practical skill prior to using the performance task-enriched material is still developing. This indicates that the ability of students to store sandwiches is limited. Students struggle to understand the practical skills of preparing store sandwiches.

As a result, the majority of respondents indicated that they had met the practical skills in terms of performance task-enriched material after using it. This implies that students' practical skills enhanced and enabled them to properly answer and execute the performance tasks. They were able to perform and present a variety of sandwiches.

Table 6 reveals the test of difference between the pretest and posttest scores of the learners in terms of perform mise'en place; prepare variety of sandwiches; present variety of sandwiches; and store sandwiches. The computed p-value was 0.000 for the perform mise'en place; prepare variety of sandwiches; present variety of sandwiches; and store sandwiches presented that there is a significant difference in the pre-test and posttest scores of the respondents in terms of practical skills: perform mise'en place; prepare variety of sandwiches; present variety of sandwiches; and store sandwiches since the p-value is less than 0.05. It implies that there is a significant improvement on their practical skills in Preparing variety of Sandwiches that students were able to achieve the proficient level in perform mise'en place and prepare variety of sandwiches of from approaching proficiency and proficient

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levels. Meanwhile, student-respondents were able to reach developing and approaching proficiency in present variety of sandwiches and store sandwiches.

As depicted in the table, there is a significant correlation between the assessed performance tasks-enriched material and practical skills in terms of perform mise'en place and in terms of introduction ($r = 0.360$, p -value < 0.0). Other correlations are not significant (p -values > 0.05 (0.01)).

Given that there is a significant correlation between the performance tasks-enriched material and the learners' practical skills, it can be inferred that the introduction used clearly influences the learner's level of skill attainment in practical skills. The researcher noted that the findings were significant, thus rejecting the null hypothesis and was confirmed by the result of statistical testing. This implies that the introduction of the assessed performance tasks-enriched material has a significant relationship with perform mise'en place.

Table 6. Test of Correlations between the Assessed Performance Tasks-Enriched Material and the Practical Skills of the Learners

Practical Skills		Posttest Mean	Std. Deviation	Pretest Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean difference	T	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Interpretation
Perform Mise'en Place		7.49	1.22	5.77	1.88	1.71	7.11	34	.000	Significant
Prepare Variety of Sandwiches		6.83	1.76	5.57	2.03	1.26	4.24	34	.000	Significant
Present Variety of Sandwiches		5.94	1.35	3.83	1.07	2.11	7.89	34	.000	Significant
Store Sandwiches		7.46	1.44	3.63	1.06	3.83	15.05	34	.000	Significant

Legend: $p < 0.05$ – Significant, $p > 0.05$ Not Significant

Table 7. Test of Correlation between the Assessed Performance Tasks-Enriched Material and the Practical Skills of the Learners

	Perform Mise'en Place	Prepare Variety of Sandwiches	Present Variety of Sandwiches	Store Sandwiches
INTRODUCTION	.360*	.324	-.067	.286
CONNECT	.055	.252	-.098	.042
APPLICATION	.035	.330	.025	.145
REFLECTION	.145	.134	-.324	.044
EXTENSION	.088	.327	-.077	.299

Legend: * Correlation is significant at .05 level (2-tailed)

In part to the r -values of objectives attainment to introduction ($r = 0.360$), whenever introduction is set in the teaching and learning process indicated in the material, this will result in a positive moderate increase in the learners' skills level in practical skills, specifically in introduction concepts, in order for them to manipulate the given in the performance task and apply contents in real life concerns.

This also signifies the approaching proficiency of the learner to which they reached proficient level in perform mise'en place due to attained introduction using the performance tasks-enriched material. It implies that the introduction in the performance task-enriched material was SMART (Specific, Measurable, Attainable, Reliable, and Time-bound). So that it supports the learning competencies established by the curriculum and allows them to apply what they have learned in real-life situations. The introduction also clarifies the material for the student, allowing them to better understand their lesson. The result was supported by the study, Cosman, [12] emphasizing the development of the concepts and objectives that will govern a procedural skills curriculum. These concepts and objectives will determine the learning experiences that must be included in the curriculum.

Based on Table 8, there is a significant correlation between perform mise'en place in terms of consistency ($r = 0.432$, p -value < 0.05) and level of present variety of sandwiches in terms of consistency ($r = 0.440$, p -value < 0.05) and the other correlations are not significant (p -values > 0.05 (0.01)).

As indicated in the table, there is a significant correlation between the learners' practical skills and the level of acceptability of the designed performance tasks-enriched material. This is evident in the consistency in the prepare mise'en place at 0.432 and the variety of sandwiches at 0.440. However, adaptability, appropriateness, usability, and aesthetic value are not significantly related to the learners' practical skills.

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Table 8. Test of Correlation between the Level of Acceptability of Performance Tasks-Enriched Material and the Practical Skills of the Learners

	Perform Mise'en Place	Prepare Variety of Sandwiches	Present Variety of Sandwiches	Store Sandwiches
ADAPTABILITY	.187	.353*	-.087	.176
APPROPRIATENESS	.275	.144	.087	.211
CONSISTENCY	.432**	.440**	.116	.152
USABILITY	.335*	.165	-.028	.315
AESTHETIC VALUE	.155	.239	-.090	.098

Legend: ** Correlation is significant at .01 level (2-tailed)

Since there is significant correlation between the level of acceptability of the designed performance tasks-enriched material and the practical skills of the learner in as to the consistency, the researcher noted that the findings were significant, thus rejecting the null hypothesis. It can be implied that the more usable material like performance task-enriched material is utilized will evidently influence the level of skills attainment of the learner in practical skills particularly in perform mise'en place and prepare variety of sandwiches.

As revealed with the r-values of consistency ($r=0.432$) and ($r=0.440$) it shows that consistency of the performance task-enriched material is needed in the practical skills of the learners' order for them to manipulate the given in the performance task and apply contents in real life concerns.

In conclusion, the characteristics of performance task-enriched material are exceptionally effective in increasing practical skills of students in terms of perform mise'en place, prepare variety of sandwiches, present variety of sandwiches and store sandwiches as shown in the preceding tables and findings. This demonstrates, in certain aspects, that the student's performance task in the use of performance task-enriched material has a positive significant relationship with their practical skills. This finding suggests that including performance task-enriched material in students' performance tasks improves their practical skills in terms of. perform mise'en place, prepare variety of sandwiches, present variety of sandwiches and store sandwiches. This explains why a significant improvement in the effectiveness of these performance task-enriched materials corresponds to a significant improvement in the learners' proficiency level in terms of practical skills. In relation to the findings of this study, as video-based instructional materials are made available to distance learners in order for them to learn practical skills at a distance, it is critical to assess their instructional effectiveness and comprehend how students respond to them. This research is the second half of a broader exploratory study that looked at the instructional effectiveness of video-based instructional resources for teaching distance learners' practical skills in block-laying and concrete, as well as how learners responded to these instructional materials. This research specifically seeks to examine learners' acceptance and satisfaction with the resources. Donkor.[13] As a result, the practical skills of the student gained from the performance task of the material, the goal they achieved from the introduction, the prior experience connected to new experience, they learned from the lesson applied into practice, reflection they wrote their experiences and struggles in the lesson, and extension helped strengthen the skills they achieve in the lesson and use it in daily life activity. Their experiences with performance task-enriched material, which engaged them in the learning process, had a positive impact on their practical skills.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn

1. From the data gathered and interpreted, it was concluded that there is a significant difference in the pre-test and posttest scores of the respondents in terms of practical skills: introduction, connecting, application, reflection, and extension. Thus, the hypothesis posited is not supported.
2. There is a significant relationship between the assessed performance task-enriched material and the level of proficiency in practical skills of the respondents. Therefore, the null hypothesis is not supported.
3. There is a significant relationship between the level of acceptability of performance task-enriched material and the level of proficiency in practical skills of the respondents. Then the null hypothesis is not supported

RECOMMENDATION

Based on the results and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are hereby suggested:

1. Since the study revealed the effectiveness of the performance tasks-enriched material in improving the practical skills of the respondents, it is suggested that a study may also be conducted using the different topics in TLE 9 Home Economics for different respondents.
2. The teachers may use the performance task-enriched material as learning and supplementary materials for all learners in their remedial classes.
3. The school administrators may support the reproduction of performance task-enriched material for this can help to improve the practical skills of the learners in their school.

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4. Future researchers may continue the study or may conduct a similar study in other components of TLE like AgriFishery Arts, Industrial Arts, and Information Computer Technology. Succeeding research may be conducted focusing on the designing of materials for other subjects at different levels. The study can be used as a continuous project to lessen the number of students who are not skilled.

5. Training and seminars about making instructional materials, workbooks, and modules are suggested to the school administrator to train the teachers in making instructional material that can help the learners to improve their academic performance.

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